

DESIGNING OPEN GOVERNMENT DATA PROGRAMS FOR USABILITY: THE IMPACT OF USABILITY ATTRIBUTES ON OPEN DATA USE

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1. Introduction

Open government advocates argue for greater access to government data in an effort to increase transparency, accountability, and participation. In recent years, scholars have investigated such claims empirically, finding evidence that open government data (OGD) can indeed foster democracy (Ruijter et al., 2017; Ruijter and Martinius, 2017), provide public value (Gurin, 2014; Janssen et al., 2012), and enhance transparency and accountability (Lourenço, 2013; Lourenço et al., 2017; Lnenicka and Nikiforova, 2021; Lnenicka et al., 2021). Of course, the value that OGD provides to governments and its stakeholders is heavily contingent on its use. Yet, scholars argue that a major barrier to open data initiatives still lies in the general lack of such use (Safarov et al., 2017; Kapoor et al., 2015). This has led to a closer look at a number of factors that shape OGD use and reuse including the general functionality and usability of open data portals (Dawes et al., 2016; Machova et al., 2018; Hogan et al., 2017; Saxena, 2017; Lourenco, 2015) and the quality and usefulness of the datasets available on them (Ansari et al., 2022; Evans and Campos, 2013; Dawes et al., 2010; Martin et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2021).

For example, a handful of studies analyze factors such as completeness, availability, and timeliness (Vetro et al., 2016), arguing that such factors are necessary for open data usability. Indeed, usability is an important antecedent of open data initiatives, and, thus, the public value, broadly defined, that may be realized by these initiatives. However, much of the research to date remains largely normative. Despite the importance of questions surrounding the relationship between usability attributes and the public's use of open data, few studies have empirically examined the effect of usability attributes on user's engagement with open data. Yet, understanding how different dimensions of usability manifest on open data portals and, in turn, impact open data use, remains critical for both the evaluation of open government programs and the design of open data platforms. If open data initiatives, especially at the local level, are to achieve their potential as tools for increased transparency, accountability, collaboration, and participation, we must understand how the design and affordances of open data portals shape the usability of government information in the form of open data and, in turn, its use.

2. Research design

This mixed-methods study seeks to address this limited perspective by answering two questions. First, to what extent are governments promoting usability of government information on their open data portals? Second, how do efforts to improve usability influence open data use? To answer these questions, this research draws on the transparency and open government literature in public administration as well as emerging user experience research in the fields of marketing and psychology. A review of the literature informed a qualitative content analysis of observational data collected from 15 cities' open data portals: Albany (NY), Austin (TX), Chicago (IL), Cincinnati (OH), Kansas City (MO), Little Rock (AR), Los Angeles (CA), Nashville (TN), New Orleans (LA), New York (NY), Orlando (FL), Richmond (VA), Salt Lake City (UT), San Francisco (CA), Seattle (WA). The metadata from 5863 total published data objects (i.e. structured datasets) were analyzed to understand how dimensions of usability manifest on the cities' open data portals. The qualitative analysis identified a number of data quality and usability attributes that were then used as independent variables in a series of linear regression models. Using the number of dataset views and dataset downloads as dependent variables, the models allowed for a quantitative analysis of the relationship between governments' efforts to improve the usability of open data and actual open data use.

3. Summary of findings

Two main conclusions were drawn from the findings of this analysis. First, the results of the qualitative analysis highlighted the disparities in data quality and usability across the 15 cities. All cities used the Socrata Inc. platform which provides cities with the opportunity to leverage the design mechanisms of the Socrata interface in order to make open data more user-friendly. Despite this equal opportunity, the findings suggest that some cities invest more effort than others in presenting data in ways that are easy for users to understand, navigate, and find what they are looking for. This was evident by the noticeable differences in how cities' metadata, how much metadata they provided users with, and the quality and usability of the information. Some cities such as Austin and San Francisco consistently provided users with the information they would need to search, understand, and use the open data available. Whereas, cities like Orlando and Salt Lake City fell short when it came to the amount of information provided and the ways in which the information was presented, evidenced by the overall lack of metadata on the cities' platforms as well as the completeness of the metadata that was available. Observable differences in the quality of data weren't just evident across the cities though; there was also considerable variation in the quality and usability of the datasets that cities were publishing on their portals.

Nonetheless, the results of the quantitative analysis were consistent and clear: data quality and usability matter for open data use. The results of the analysis showed that leaving fields empty or neglecting to include keywords had significant (negative) impacts on open data use. On the other hand, relatively simple steps such as providing a dataset description or category had significant and sizable impacts on the number of views and downloads of a dataset. In some cases, a complete description increased the number of views by more than 230%. Therefore, governments' efforts to improve the usability of open data by presenting information in a clear, concise, and easy-to-understand manner can really pay off for open data use.

Still, all efforts are not equal, which was the second conclusion drawn. Findings suggest that efforts to improve intrinsic data quality such as ensuring completeness of administrative metadata, including tags and keywords, and a human-readable name and description for the data object had significant positive effects on both dataset views and downloads. Additionally, dimensions of contextual data quality that provide users with the necessary metadata to assist with discoverability and understandability of relevant data were positively associated with open data use. However, some usability attributes were significantly more effective at increasing views, a form of engagement that could be considered more passive in this context, while others were significantly more effective at increasing downloads, a more active form of engagement. The former might imply that the data are available to provide citizens with a “window” into the inner workings of the government while the latter is indicative of use and reuse that can support collaboration and innovation. Thus, cities may find that investing time and effort into improving one particular area of data quality and usability is a better use of resources than others, depending on their goals.

4. Theoretical & practical contributions of research

This research advances the literature in three main ways. First, in contrast to previous studies, this study combines observational data from the open data portals of 15 cities in the U.S. with two quantitative measures of use, views and downloads of each individual dataset, to understand how usability attributes shape open data use. To date, research relies mostly on attitudinal perceptions of public managers and citizens toward open data as well as researchers’ observations of open data portals to draw conclusions about what factors are important for open data usability (Machova et al., 2018; Ojo et al., 2018). This study’s research design, thus, offers the opportunity to not only explore how cities are promoting usability of open data but empirically test the relationship between the attributes of usability discussed throughout the literature and measures of actual open data use. Scholars have been calling for more empirical investigations into the many assumptions made about open data utilization (Safarov et al., 2017), including more quantitative research (Hossain et al., 2016) that aims to provide inferential analyses on open data and its outcomes (Thorsby et al., 2017). Therefore, this study aims to answer this call. Second, despite critiques that research on open data and similar ICT-based interventions lack sufficient theoretical foundation (Charalabadis et al., 2016; Begany and Gil-Garcia, 2021), using this novel research design, this study empirically tests claims made about governments’ efforts to improve usability and effects on actual open data use, advancing theoretical understanding of how governments can more effectively leverage the affordances of open data programs and platforms to engage the public in ways relevant to democratic outcomes. Lastly, this study aims to inform a greater understanding of the design attributes that help or hinder user experience with open data platforms. While usability, similar to other dimensions of user experience, can be subjective and often difficult to understand without directly observing user behavior, the results of this study suggest that some best practices have considerable influence on open data use. As such, this paper concludes with a discussion of the affordances of open data portals and design principles that government agencies should keep in mind when designing, implementing, and managing open data portals. These affordances and design principles can help governments not only improve usability but also align their efforts with both broad-level and targeted strategic goals.

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